

Intermediates in Hantzsch Synthesis and Synthesis of Symmetrical Thioethers (I).

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Thioacetamide and α or β functionalised halides in alkaline medium formed symmetrical thioethers (I). In condensations with thioacetamide in acidic medium α -haloketones gave thiazoles through 4-hydroxy- Δ^2 -thiazolinium salts. 4-Chlorobutan-2-one gave 4-acetylthiolobutan-2-one (VII).

THE Hantzsch synthesis involving the condensation of thiourea or thioamide moiety with an α -halocarbonyl derivative has been extensively used in synthesising a variety of thiazoles¹, thiazoloheterocyclics and their salts². In these reactions the intermediacy of hydroxythiazolidines³ and hydroxy thiazolinium salts⁴ has been reported. An evidence for hydroxythiazolidines which undergo facile dehydration under acidic conditions of Hantzsch reaction was provided by the isolation of these intermediates in the reactions of cyclic thioureas with α or β -haloketones under alkaline conditions⁵. Here the results of the reactions of thioacetamide with α or β -halocarbonyl derivatives under different reaction conditions are reported.

Thioacetamide and ω -bromoacetophenone in aqueous sodium hydroxide formed 2-methyl-4-phenylthiazole and a major product which was devoid of

elemental nitrogen. It showed the presence of C=O (i.r.) and absence of CH₃(nmr) and was assigned structure I, (n=1, R=COC₆H₅)⁶. Similar condensations of thioacetamide with *p*-methyl- ω -chloroacetophenone, *p*-chloro- ω -chloroacetophenone, benzyl chloride, ethyl bromoacetate, ethyl- β -bromopropionate, 4-chlorobutan-2-one and β -bromopropiophenone gave I (n=1, R=COC₆H₄-CH₃p), (n=1, R=COC₆H₄-Clp), (n=1, R=C₆H₅), (n=1, R=COOC₂H₅), (n=2, R=-COOC₂H₅), (n=2, R=-COCH₃), (n=2, R=COC₆H₅) respectively as the major products. The reaction with chloroacetone gave a multitude of products from which thioether could not be isolated. Thioacetamide and ω -bromoacetophenone, in aprotic solvents formed 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-4-phenyl- Δ^2 -thiazolinium bromide (V, R'=C₆H₅) but in ethanol solution containing a catalytic amount of acid, 2-methyl-4-phenylthiazole (VI, R'=C₆H₅) was isolated. Similar results were obtained in case of bromoacetone and thioacetamide.

Amongst the reactions of β -haloketones, 4-chlorobutan-2-one and thioacetamide in anhydrous ethanol in the presence of an acid formed ammonium chloride and a product, M^+ , m/e 146. In its mass spectrum the two most intense peaks appeared at m/e 103 ($M^+ - \dot{C}OCH_3$) and m/e 71 ($M^+ - \dot{S}COCH_3$). In its i.r. spectrum, it showed two carbonyl group absorption bands at 1720 and 1690 cm^{-1} . In the nmr spectrum, the two 3H singlets at δ 2.0 and δ 2.2 and a 4H multiplet at δ 2.4-3.3 appeared. It was assigned the structure, 4-acetylthiolobutan-2-one (VII). β -Bromopropiophenone in a similar reaction was recovered unchanged.

In these reactions, the first step would evidently be the formation of II. Under alkaline conditions, it underwent hydrolytic cleavages of C=N and C-S bonds and the thiolate ion (IV) thus generated, *in situ*, through nucleophilic substitution of another molecule of the halide, furnished I. Under acidic conditions, II ($n=1$, $R=COCH_3$, COC_6H_5) formed from corresponding α -haloketones provided Hantzsch reaction product but II ($n=2$, $R=COCH_3$) formed from 4-chlorobutan-2-one where cyclisation to thiazine ring was relatively difficult⁷, gave (VII).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillaries. For T. L. C., plates were coated with silica gel G and spots were developed with iodine. Chloroform or $CHCl_3$: C_2H_5OH (95:5, V/V) were used as solvents for T. L. C. Elemental analyses were performed at Australian Microanalytical Service, CSIRO, University of Melbourne, Victoria, Australia. I. R. spectra were recorded on specord 71 instrument in chloroform solution. N. M. R. spectra were run on a Tesla BSU 87C, 80 MHz instrument, in $CDCl_3$ solutions.

1. *Condensation of thioacetamide and halides: General procedure.* Thioacetamide (.01 mole) was dissolved in an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (.01 mole) and a solution of the halides (.01 mole) in ethanol (10-15 ml) was added with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight. The solid products were filtered; otherwise the products were isolated by extraction with chloroform and were purified through column chromatography. The compounds (I) prepared, adsorbants used in column chromatography, melting points, solvents of crystallisation, percentage yields, i.r., n.m.r. spectra and analysis are listed below:

(i) I, $n=1$, $R=COC_6H_5$: alumina; 67°-68°; ethanol; 95% ν_{max} 1680 cm^{-1} ; δ 3.92 (4H, S), δ 7.2-8.0 (10H, m) (Found: C, 70.47; H, 5.25; S, 11.6, $C_{18}H_{14}SO_2$ requires C, 70.11; H, 5.18, S, 11.8%).

(ii) I, $n=1$, $R=COC_6H_4-CH_3p$: alumina; 85°-86°; ethanol; 93% ν_{max} 1675 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.4 (6H, S), δ 3.87 (4H, S); δ 7.3-8.2 (8H, m). (Found: C, 72.06; H, 6.07; S, 10.7, $C_{18}H_{14}SO_2$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.04; S, 11.11%).

(iii) I, $n=1$, $R=COC_6H_4-Clp$: alumina; 110°; 94% ν_{max} 1675 cm^{-1} ; δ 3.9 (4H, S), δ 7.5-8.3 (8H, m). (Found: 57.15; H, 3.56; S, 9.4, $C_{16}H_{12}SO_2Cl_2$ requires C, 56.70; H, 3.54; S, 9.4%).

(iv) I, $n=1$, $R=C_6H_5$: alumina; 49°; ethanol; 90%; (Found: M^+ m/e 214 (mass spectrum). $C_{14}H_{14}S$ requires molecular weight 214).

(v) I, $n=2$, $R=COCH_3$: silicagel; liquid; 58%; ν_{max} 1715 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.13 (6H, S), δ 2.2 (4H, S). (Found: M^+ m/e 174 (mass spectrum). $C_8H_{14}SO_2$ requires molecular weight 174).

(vi) I, $n=2$, $R=COC_6H_5$: alumina; 95°; ethanol; 96% ν_{max} 1680 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.8-3.5 (8H, A_2B_2 pattern), δ 7.3-8.0 (10H, m). (Found: C, 72.4; H, 6.20; S, 10.60, $C_{18}H_{14}SO_2$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.04; S, 11.11%).

(vii) I, $n=1$, $R=-COOC_6H_5$: silicagel; liquid; 85%; ν_{max} 1730 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.38 (6H, t, $J=6H_s$), δ 4.22 (4H, q, $J=6Hz$), δ 3.35 (4H, S). (Found: M^+ , m/e 206 (mass spectrum). $C_9H_{14}SO_2$ requires molecular weight 206).

(viii) I, $n=2$, $R=-COOC_2H_5$: silicagel; liquid; 87% ν_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.25 (6H, t, $J=7Hz$), δ 4.72 (4H, q, $J=7Hz$), δ 2.8 (4H, t, $J=7Hz$), δ 3.52 (4H, t, $J=7H_s$). (Found: M^+ , m/e 234 (mass spectrum). $C_{10}H_{14}O_4S$ requires molecular weight 234).

2. *2-Methyl-4-phenyl-4-hydroxy- Δ^2 -thiazolinium bromide* $V, R'=-C_6H_5$): ω -Bromoacetophenone (1.9g, .01 mole) dissolved in anhydrous acetone, ether or tetrahydrofuran was added to a solution of thioacetamide (0.75g, .01 mole) in the same solvent. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath for 5-10 min and was cooled. The product separated was collected and washed several times with the solvent, m.p. 85° (yield 90%). (Found: N, 4.59; S, 11.3, $C_{10}H_{11}NO$ SBr requires N, 5.1; S, 11.6%).

3. *2-Methyl-4-phenyl thiazole* (VI, $R'=C_6H_5$): (a) (V, $R'=C_6H_5$) was suspended in ether and was basified with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal layer was separated, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether was removed from the extract. The residue was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 52°-53°. (Found: C, 68.38; H, 5.31, N, 8.08; S, 17.6, $C_{10}H_9NS$ requires C, 68.57; H, 5.14; N, 8.00, S, 17.28%). (b) A solution of thioacetamide (0.75g, .01 mole) in absolute alcohol (25 ml) acidified with hydrogen chloride gas and ω -bromoacetophenone was refluxed for 6 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue was suspended in ether and was basified with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent was

^a A faster moving minor product (5%), identical (TLC, mmp) with an authentic sample of 2-methyl-4-phenylthiazole was also isolated.

^b Another slow moving minor product was isolated but it was not characterised.

removed. The residue was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 52°-53° and was found to be identical (mmp, R_f) with the product obtained in (a).

4. 2, 4-Dimethyl -4-hydroxy- Δ^2 -Thiazolinium bromide ($V, R' = CH_3$): was obtained from bromoacetone and thioacetamide as in expt. 2. (Found: N, 6.72; S, 15.40; C_8H_9 SOBr requires N, 6.63; S, 15.10%).

5. 2, 4-Dimethylthiazole ($VI, R' = CH_3$): was obtained by basification of ($V, R' = CH_3$) as well as by the condensation of bromoacetone with thioacetamide in acidified ethanolic solution as in expt. 3. (Found: N, 12.2; S, 28.6; C_5H_7NS requires N, 12.4; S, 28.3%). NMR: δ 2.3 (3H, S), δ 2.56 (3H, S), δ 6.35(1H, S).

6. 4-Acetylthiobutan-2-one (VII): A solution of thioacetamide (.01 mole) and 4-chlorobutan-2-one (.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol containing hydrogen chloride gas was refluxed for 30 min. It was cooled and ammonium chloride separated was collected. From the filtrate, the solvent was removed and the residue made alkaline with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. It was extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried and the solvent was removed. The residue was purified in a column packed with alumina and the product was isolated as thick brown liquid. (Found M^+ , m/e 146 (mass spectrum). $C_6H_{10}SO_2$ requires

molecular weight 146). ν_{max} 1690, 1720 cm^{-1} . NMR: δ 2.0 (3H, S), δ 2.2(3H, S), δ 2.4-3.0(4H, m).

When the same reaction was run by refluxing the reaction mixture in anhydrous acetone, the reactants remained unchanged. But in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran solution, ammonium chloride was deposited and the product from the mother liquor could not be isolated.

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